

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPATIAL PERSPECTIVE IMAGERY IN THE PERFORMANCE OF PENCIL AND DRAFT IN THE PROCESS OF STUDENT EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: Everything we draw in the paper takes place in space, and it is not an easy task to reflect the specific and distinct location of the subject in space, thus giving the subject a three-dimensional quality on paper. That's why we use vertical and horizontal planes to help us draw. Wherever we look, our eyes create imaginary planes. When drawing, we use only horizontal planes that are parallel to the earth's surface. In this article, the theoretical importance of perspectival depiction in different perspectives is highlighted.

Keywords: vertical, horizontal, horizon, parallel, paper, plane, square, axis.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada biz chizgan har bir narsa makonda sodir bo'ladi va sub'ektning fazodagi o'ziga xos va alohida o'rnini aks ettirish oson ish emas, shu tariqa mavzuga qog'ozda uch o'lchovli xususiyat beradi. Shuning uchun rasm chizishda bizga yordam berish uchun vertikal va gorizontal tekisliklardan foydalanamiz. Qayerga qarasak, ko'zlarimiz xayoliy samolyotlarni yaratadi. Chizish paytida biz faqat er yuzasiga parallel bo'lgan gorizontal tekisliklardan foydalanamiz. Ushbu maqolada tasvirlashni turli rakurslarda perispektiv jihatdan tasvirlashni qonuniyatlar asosida tasvirlashni nazariy ahamiyati akslantirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: vertikal, gorizontal, ufq, parallel, qog'oz, tekislik, kvadrat, o'q.

Аннотация: Все, что мы рисуем на бумаге, происходит в пространстве, и это непростая задача — отразить конкретное и отчетливое расположение предмета в пространстве, тем самым придав предмету трехмерность на бумаге. Вот почему мы используем вертикальные и горизонтальные плоскости, чтобы рисовать. Куда бы мы ни посмотрели, наши глаза создают воображаемые плоскости. При рисовании мы используем только горизонтальные плоскости, параллельные земной поверхности. В данной статье подчеркивается теоретическая важность перспективного изображения в разных ракурсах.

Ключевые слова: вертикаль, горизонталь, горизонт, параллель, бумага, плоскость, квадрат, ось.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular,

the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time" 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

Nowadays, art needs to make human life more beautiful, to provide aesthetic and spiritual nourishment to a person. It should inspire people to work and live, enrich their inner world. Human spiritual world always needs examples of art. Therefore, it is impossible to live without art.

The space between the artist and the still life, landscape, portrait, etc., which is described as the picture plane. From a physiological point of view, light falls on the object being drawn, and the artist sees the shape of this or that part.[4]

Only after that, the artist perceives it and proceeds to describe it. The plane of the picture serves as a medium between the artist and nature. The plane of the object is the plane on which the depicted object is located. An object plane can be a table, floor, ground, or other drawing device.

The field of view is the extent to which the artist can see the object being depicted. As the artist moves away from the depicted object, his field of vision expands, which makes it possible to clearly see and depict all parts of the depicted object. But standing at a great distance from the object, it is very difficult to fully describe all its parts and volumes. We are in infinite space. At the same time, students' memories are strengthened, vocabulary is increased. [5] Everything we draw takes place in space, and it is not an easy task to reflect the specific and distinct location of the subject in space, thus giving the subject a three-dimensional quality on paper. That's why we use vertical and horizontal

planes to help us draw. Wherever we look, our eyes create imaginary planes. When drawing, we use only horizontal planes that are parallel to the earth's surface.

We can see very far in an airplane; We call the line between the sky and the earth "horizon". Similarly, we call this plane that our eyes perceive, which extends parallel to the ground and ends at the horizon, a horizontal plane. Everything we want to draw is above or below this plane. A teenager begins to organize his activities on the basis of a particular principle, belief, and personal point of view. [6] Looking down, we see things on the plane, looking up, we see things below the plane. Objects located directly above the horizontal plane require a special description; For example, a piece of paper can look like a line.

Wherever we look, our eyes create imaginary planes. When drawing, only the horizontal plane parallel to the ground is used from these planes. The vertical plane intersects the horizontal plane at right angles. When we look at something, our eyes also perceive imaginary vertical planes. However, in drawing, only a plane that intersects the horizontal plane at right angles will work for us.

The vertical plane is perpendicular to the horizontal plane. Together they divide the space into four parts. If we were to represent the two planes by drawing two lines intersecting each other at right angles, we would have to draw an imaginary cross intersecting at right angles.

The horizontal plane divides space into two horizontal parts, and everything we draw is below, above, or just above that line.

A vertical plane divides space into two vertical segments, and everything we draw is to the right, left, or above that line.

Understanding and being able to use the rules of perspective is very useful when drawing objects or living things.

Perspective refers to the angle of view. In visual arts, it represents the relationship of objects, shapes and bodies in three-dimensional space to other elements in the painting or to the artist himself. There are two important rules of

perspective:

Parallels intersect at infinity, including parallel lines and planes. Consider a path that is parallel to each other, such as train tracks or sidewalks: train tracks or tracks always seem to run toward each other.

The second important rule is that objects closer to the viewer appear larger than objects of the same size but further away. Electric poles are a good example of this.

A square has four equal sides. Opposite sides are parallel to each other, and adjacent sides are perpendicular to each other. Here you will see a square that is bisected horizontally and vertically.

If you tilt the square back with the horizontal plane bisecting the square as an axis, the backmost side is still parallel to the axis and closer to us, but away from the axis.

You will notice that it looks shorter than the leading edge. The lateral edges are of equal length, but extend towards each other and appear to intersect at a point in the vertical plane. The farther a square is from the viewer, the larger it appears when viewed from above or below. Let's imagine that the field is the

door we are opening. As the distance between its vertical edges decreases, its horizontal edges move and come closer to each other; at the same time, he moves further and further away from the person looking at the picture. This new shape of the square also bends. If

you do this, you will again have a general square shape. Opposite sides move closer to each other as they move away from the viewer.

If you do this, you will again have a general square shape. Opposite sides move closer to each other as they move away from the viewer.

It is not easy to predict how much parallel edges will move closer or farther apart. So, I suggest you put two pencils on the lines. So you can easily check whether the drawing is correct or not. Note: If

the edges are parallel or converge as you approach them, the drawing is incorrect. The angle between the vertex and the horizontal and vertical planes and the direction of the adjacent sides can be found by holding the measuring stick horizontally or vertically at the corner of the square. One of the most common mistakes in inexperienced drawings is edges that stretch in the wrong direction.

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To determine the length of a square in its general position, mark with a

measuring stick, holding one end at the furthest corner and the other end horizontally. The overall width of the square is also found with a measuring stick held vertically.

You can measure one side of the square with a measuring

stick that you hold straight and use it as a unit of measure for the rest of the drawing.

In conclusion, it should be said that the theoretical basis of depicting things from different perspectives in three dimensions has been achieved.

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